

POSITIVE EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCES WITH PORTABLE INTERACTIVE PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

Positive emotions are central to human life and have implications to the overall quality of people's life (Fredrickson, 1998). This paper reports on positive experiences with two types of portable interactive devices (PIDs), specifically media/entertainment and medical/health devices. The study is based on a six-month longitudinal study exploring people's emotional experience and how PIDs mediate these experiences in everyday contexts. Previous findings by the authors (Gomez, Popovic & Blackler, 2011) presented four categories of activities including Feature, Functional, Mediation and Auxiliary activities and their relationship to emotional experience. The paper presents emotional experiences with specific activities reported with a focus on positive emotions. It concludes with a discussion of the findings on positive experiences and the implications for the future design of PIDs.

Keywords: Design and emotion, positive emotional experiences, portable interactive devices

INTRODUCTION

Designers who do not take into account emotional aspect of human experiences will inevitably develop artefacts and systems that ignore basic human needs and desires. A crucial part of this understanding is exploring how, to what extent, and in what way positive emotions are facilitated or hindered through interactions with products in daily life. Portable interactive devices (PIDs) are unique because they are carried and interacted with in diverse contexts; alone or with other people, privately or publically. As such people's relationship with PIDs, and their

emotional experiences, can be unique and distinctive in ways that other products cannot.

This paper presents a longitudinal study that explored the emotional experience of two product categories including media / entertainment PIDs (MP3 players and PDAs with mobile telephone functionality) and medical / health PIDs (blood-glucose monitors, pedometers and heart-rate monitors). The authors have previously published findings from this experiment outlining the impact of the social level on the overall emotional experience. It was identified that negative and positive social experiences have different impacts on the emotional experience with PIDs (Gomez, Popovic & Blackler, 2009; 2010). Further, the authors also presented four categories of activities with PIDs including Feature, Functional, Mediation and Auxiliary activities that constituted emotional experiences. It was found that for both PID types Feature related activities were identified as negative in nature. Functional activities were characterised as mainly positive for both PID types. Likewise Mediation activities were identified as overwhelmingly positive for both PIDs while Auxiliary activities were characterised as significantly negative in nature (Gomez, Popovic & Blackler, 2011).

Additional findings are presented in this paper regarding specific positive emotional experiences within the Functional and Mediation Activity Categories (the two activity categories characterised as positive in nature). Although there has been research that proposes that designing to elicit or prevent a particular emotion is possible (Demir, Desmet & Hekkert, 2009), the approach taken here is that specific emotional reactions are difficult to elicit through the design of a product. Rather, the intent is

to design devices that more broadly facilitate or help promote positive experiences over time in context, instead of eliciting specific emotions from users. It is envisioned that the findings presented here contribute and build on existing knowledge of the evolving emotional experience with products, especially with PIDs.

POSITIVE EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCES AND PIDS

Emotions have a significant role to play in how people feel about themselves and about their life experiences. Positive emotions have an added level of importance in everyday life and are closely tied in with overall health and well-being. Experiences of positive emotions are core to human life and are intertwined with people's overall quality of life (Fredrickson, 1998). As Ryff and Singer (1998) point out that positive health, as defined by the World Health Organisation, is a "state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity" (p.1). Using this definition as a benchmark it is important to consider the way products relate to overall well-being by either facilitating or hindering emotional experiences in everyday life.

MEDICAL AND HEALTH DEVICES

Gloyd (2003) argues that well designed medical products lead to increased patient adherence to medical regimes and that design takes on a crucial role in patient therapy, "a pleasurable user experience with medical devices is a critical component in the process that leads to adherence to medical recommendations" (p.17). As such emotions affect the way people feel about their health not just at a psychological level, but also at a physical and physiological level (Mayne, 2001). However, as Xue, Yen, Boucharenc and Choolani (2008) outline "...little published work exists on the ergonomics aspects of medical device development... even less advice available to designers on which issues to consider taking into account the essential characteristics for good design" (p.413). Although there is literature to support the idea that emotions are critical for medical devices to assist with people's health (Pentland, 2004; Shah, 2005; Reiner, 2008) there is little research available that touches on how design impacts

emotional experiences, especially in regards to facilitating positive emotional experiences over time.

MEDIA AND ENTERTAINMENT DEVICES

Positive emotions of user experience have implications for how work and leisure is facilitated in daily life through the use of media and entertainment devices. Research suggests that in some contexts a pleasurable experience might increase the perceived ease-of-use of a device (Tractinsky, Katz & Iker, 2000; Hassenzahl, 2004). Apart from research relating to mobile telephones (Karapanos, Zimmerman, Forlizzi & Martens, 2009, 2010; Vincent, 2006; Jones & Marsden, 2006; Arvola, 2004; Ito, Okabe & Matsuda, 2005; Ling, 2004), few studies have explored emotional aspects of use with other media and entertainment devices. Exceptions include Stelmaszewska, Blanford and Fields (2005), Heye & Lamont (2005) and Kallinen (2004) who performed studies exploring emotional aspects with MP3 players, PDAs and other electronic devices although they did not specifically look at the evolving emotional experience of interaction over time in the same way as the current study. Two studies by Karapanos et al. (2009; 2010) seems to be the most relevant here. The first exploratory study (Karapanos et al., 2009) followed six individuals using an Apple iPhone from purchase through to 5 weeks of interaction. The second study (Karapanos et al., 2010) explored the use of mobile telephones over the course of six months. These studies are relevant in regards to the longitudinal approach and the exploration of emotional aspects of interaction in context.

ACTIVITY THEORY

Activity Theory is used as the theoretical framework to contextualise interactions between people and PIDs. As Kaptelinin (1996) argues Activity Theory holds the most promising conceptual model for studies of human-computer interaction. One of the more pertinent aspects of activity theory is that although it focuses on artefacts they act as mediators for human experience. The focus is on the human experience within everyday life and how artefacts mediate and possibly enhance this experience (Nardi, 1996). Three central features of Activity Theory that relate to this research include the focus on; (1) activities through time; (2) activities within context and (3) considering

people not merely as agents in a system but rather as having motives, intentions and emotions.

A detailed analysis of Activity theory within the context of the research has previously been presented (Gomez, Popovic & Blackler, 2010, 2011). The main aspect to highlight is that activities are composed of three levels with *activities* sitting at the highest level, which are composed of *actions*, which in turn are composed of *operations* at the lowest level (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Activities framework: levels of activities (Authors, 2005)

This model presented in Figure 1 explains a complex interaction dynamic in a simplified manner. For instance, to make a call with a mobile telephone a number is dialed (*operation*), a conversation ensues (*action*) and a message is communicated (*activity*). The model also takes into account the dynamic nature of activities. If in the attempt to make a call the mobile telephone does not function, the *activity* changes to finding out what the problem is, while the *action* may involve looking for error messages or checking for a signal, and *operation* includes pressing buttons and so forth. This highlights the fact that activities are neither static nor one-dimensional. Tasks exist on multiple levels simultaneously consisting of global-level (in broad context) and local-level (specific activities of interaction). In relation to this study the global-level is composed of the overall emotional experiences perceived by the participants during each month and at the end of the study, while the local-level is composed of the multitude of experiences recorded throughout that time. The findings presented in this paper relate to tasks at the local-level.

EMOTIONS

Within the context of this study emotions were distinguished using the Emotional Chart (Figure 2). This chart is adapted from Russell's (2003) circumplex of core affect and has been used as an effective self-reporting method in other studies investigating emotional experiences and reactions to products (Gomez, 2005; Gomez, Popovic & Blackler 2011; Desmet, 2002; Fagerberg, Stahl, & Hook, 2004).

The chart identifies the basic emotion occurring at any given moment through two dimensions: the horizontal dimension consisting of unhappy through neutral to happy, and the vertical dimension consisting of calm through neutral to excited. This chart was used as the set of basic emotions participants could refer to so as to record their emotional reactions.

Figure 2. Emotional Chart (Gomez, 2005; After Russell, 2003)

Alongside the Emotional Chart, participants had the opportunity to write down and describe their emotional reactions to support their annotations on the chart.

EXPERIMENTS

Two experiments were conducted exploring the emotional experience of interacting with media/entertainment and medical/health PIDs during everyday use over six months. This paper reports on the latest set of findings relating to positive experiences of specific activities conducted providing insights into the ways people interact with PIDs in daily life and how they in turn impact the evolving emotional experience in a positive way. The findings provide a more holistic understanding about positive experiences with portable devices to support positive emotional experiences in everyday situations. The

experimental method, approach, aims and objectives have been outlined in detail previously (Gomez et al., 2011).

Overall 651 experiences were recorded and analysed during the experiment. This included 426 experiences for media / entertainment and 225 experiences for medical / health PID category. Participants included staff members at the Queensland University of Technology as well as white-collar professionals living and working in Brisbane, Australia, with ages ranging from 21 to over 65. Only users with no more than two months experience with the devices were recruited; thus attempting to capture the initial stages of interaction and how it evolved over the six months of use.

METHOD

A triangulation approach consisting of diaries, interviews and co-discovery techniques was used. The experiment was divided into the following four stages: (1) initial interview (2) experience diaries, (3) intermittent interviews and (4) co-discovery. All audio and textual data emerging from the study were analysed using Atlas.ti software.

Initial interview

The initial interview centered on gaining knowledge about the participant's expectations of the product, initial emotions toward the product, and expected benefits it might provide.

Experience diaries

Participants were asked to fill out the diary once a week. The diaries included questions relating to the context of interaction, the activity performed, who was present during interactions, and an indication of emotional experiences. Participants recorded the emotional experience using the Emotional Chart (Figure 2).

Intermittent Interviews

Between two and three consultations were performed in the first month, followed by one a month for the remaining five months. Participants were asked questions on the number of times they had used the product since the previous interview, feelings towards the product, positive experiences of using the product,

negative experiences of using the product, and the positive or negative impact of the surrounding context (environment or social).

Co-discovery

The final part of the study involved a co-discovery session between two and three participants. This part of the study focused on how their expectations in the beginning changed as their experiences with the products evolved over the six-month period.

ANALYSIS

All data was analysed using content analysis technique (Bauer and Gaskell, 2000; Flick, 2006), in combination with thematic analysis (Boyatzis, 1998). To assist in contextualising the findings the data sets were split into two categories; local-level experiences and global-level experiences. Data relating to specific activities within the overall six-month timeframe were categorised as local-level experiences. For example, using the MP3 player to listen to a song on a train or checking the heart-rate monitor to determine heart rate would be a local-level experience. This paper reports on the analysis of the local-level interactions from initial interviews, experience diaries and intermittent interviews.

Coding Scheme

Since the focus was on determining interactions that influenced the emotional experience it was relevant to define the types of activities. A coding scheme was developed with three broad themes; Context, Emotional Perception and Tasks. Tables 1 and 2 outline the Task categories, sub-categories and associated codes for media/entertainment and medical/health PIDs respectively.

The sub-categories and codes for Tasks could only be developed during the coding process itself, as participant activities could not be predicted beforehand. For example, an excerpt from the interviews outlines how the Calendar sub-category for media/entertainment PID on Table 1 was defined:

It is convenient for me... I have something that I can make appointments on the go and if someone says let's meet tomorrow I know when I am available...

Category	Sub-Categories	Codes
Feature	Interface	AMI
	Headphones	AMH
	Sound Quality	AMQ
	Portability	AMB
	Technology	AMT
	Aesthetics	AMA
	Memory capacity	AMCP
Functional	Music / Songs	AMS
	Podcasts / Sound files	AMP
	Calendar	AMC
	Contacting people	AMCT
	GPS	AMGP
	Pictures / camera	AMPT
	TV	AMTV
	Games	AMG
	Generic work function	AMW
	Transporting product	AMTR
Mediation	Relaxation	AMR
	Escape	AME
	Companionship	AMCF
	Product becomes part of background use	AMZ
	Conscious awareness of product	AMCS
	Association of particular cultural group	AMAS
Auxiliary	Mobile phone (cell) reception	AMRN
	Battery	AMBT
	Loosing product	AML
	Damaging product	AMD

Table 1. Media / Entertainment PIDs Coding Scheme for Task theme

The participant identified the activity of using the calendar function for appointments into the PDA as a convenient function of the product. In this case the Functional sub-category AMC (Calendar) was developed as outlined on Table 1.

Another example is an excerpt from a participant that identifies both the Interface and Data storage sub-categories for medical/health PIDs on Table 2:

So I can have a look at how I'm doing...just flick back and have a look. The watch itself has also got a couple of things built in... so I can go, just by looking

at the watch I can go back about six to eight weeks um, on history [and] events.

Here the participant identifies an aspect relating to the product's interface (...I can have a look at how I'm doing... Just flick back and have a look) as well as the data storage capabilities of the product itself (...I can go back about six to eight weeks...on history [and] events). In this way the Feature sub-categories AHI (Interface) and AHDS (Data storage) were developed. All of the sub-categories were developed in this manner for both product categories.

Category	Sub-categories	Codes
Feature	Comfort	AHU
	Data storage	AHDS
	Aesthetics	AHA
	Portability	AHB
	Quality of mechanism / product	AHQ
	Interface	AHI
	Technology	AHT
	Rattling	AHR
	Alarm	AHAL
	Changing needle	AHN
	Changing strips	AHST
	Logging of data	AHLG
	Strap	AHSP
	Beeping	AHBP
	Resetting	AHRS
Functional	Recording steps	AHS
	Taking blood sample	AHP
	Reading hear rate	AHH
	Tread function	AHFI
	Timing	AHTM
	Telling time	AHTT
Mediation	Monitoring personal fitness	AHF
	Product just another item to carry	AHW
	Motivator	AHM
	Consciousness of product	AHCS
	Becomes part of background	AHZ
	Monitoring personal health	AHMH
	Reliance on product	AHRL
Auxiliary	Loosing product	AHL
	Brochure / manual	AHBR
	Damaging product	AHD
	Maintenance	AHWM
	Product broken	AHBK

Table 2. Medical / Health PIDs Coding Scheme for Task theme

Media/Entertainment Category	Positive %	Negative %
Feature	37%	63%
Functional	60%	40%
Mediation	80%	20%
Auxiliary	12%	88%

Medical/Health Categories	Positive %	Negative %
Feature	37%	63%
Functional	59%	41%
Mediation	85%	15%
Auxiliary	7%	93%

Table 3. Overall percentages for Task categories in the Media / Entertainment (top) and Medical / Health (bottom) PIDs

Task Categories

The procedure above explains how the sub-categories of both product types were initially developed from the actual experiences performed by the participants. Once the sub-categories were outlined these were grouped into comprehensive broader categories that encapsulated these tasks. For example the sub-categories in Table 2, including Interface, Headphones, Sound Quality, Portability, Technology, Aesthetics and Memory Capacity all represented features relating to the product in question and as such the category Feature was developed to encapsulate these. The remaining categories including Functions (specific functions of the products), Mediation (a task that facilitated broader activities beyond the functional) and Auxiliary (tertiary type of task) were developed using the same process.

FINDINGS

Once the data were analysed some relevant findings regarding relationships between the different Task Categories and emotional experiences across both product types were explored. Table 3 shows the overall percentages of positive and negative emotional experiences of Task Categories for media/entertainment and medical/health PIDs. Initial findings have been presented earlier (Gomez et al., 2009, 2010, 2011) and Table 3 outlines the final results for the overall percentages of the four Task Categories.

POSITIVE EXPERIENCES

The focus of attention in this paper is on positive emotions. As such the two categories that are highlighted in Table 3, Functional and Mediation for both product types, will be discussed in more depth. That is not to dismiss the relevance of negative emotions since they too, form part of the overall experience; nevertheless the focus of this paper is on the positive emotions during the overall experience.

As illustrated in Table 3, the two Activity categories characterised as overall positive include Functional and Mediation for both product types. For media/entertainment Functional experiences were noted as 60% positive while Mediation experiences were 80% positive. With medical/health Functional experiences were 59% positive while Mediation were

rated 89% positive. It is relevant to underscore that for both PID types the Functional and Mediation activities were characterised as positive in nature and also to a similar value. This indicates there might be consistent perceptions about the way people feel regarding these types of experiences with PIDs. As part of the coding, positive and negative experiences relating to the specific sub-categories were also recorded. For instance the number of times participants mentioned using the heart rate monitor in a positive and/or negative way to read their heart rate (Code AHH, Table 2) was also coded. Figures 3 and 4 illustrate the sub-categories for each of the PID types under Functional and Mediation coded as positive or negative.

Figure 3. Media / Entertainment Functional and Mediation sub-categories and corresponding positive and negative percentages

Media / Entertainment PIDs

Figure 3 highlights the distribution of positive and negative experiences for Functional (top) and Mediation (bottom) experiences for media / entertainment PIDs.

Looking more closely at Functional category it can be noted that Music / Songs (listening to music) was highest with 23% of experiences rated as positive. This was followed by; Contacting people (making calls and sending texts) with 10% positive; Generic work function (using device for work-related purposes) with 7% positive; Calendar (using calendar feature) with 6%; and Podcast / Sound files (listening to specific podcast or sound file) with 5%. The remaining sub-categories including GPS, Pictures / Cameras, TV, Games and Transporting product were only experienced minimally. Although Music / Songs and Contacting people were rated highly positive it can also be seen that they were also highest with negative experiences in the group. Further, Podcasts / Sound files was the only activity in which negative experiences outweighed positive experiences.

Focusing on the Mediation category it can be seen that Escape (activity in which device facilitated escapism) was overwhelmingly highest with 51% of experiences rated as positive. This was followed by: Relaxation (device allowed user to relax) with 16% positive, and Companionship (use of product giving user companionship) and Product diffuses into background (the product is used but is not consciously thought about) both with 7% positive experiences. Association with cultural group (user felt like they were associated with other people using the same product, i.e. "iPod users") was the only activity categorised more negative than positive.

Medical / Health PIDs

Figure 4 illustrates the distribution of positive and negative experiences for Functional (top) and Mediation (bottom) experiences for medical / health PIDs.

Looking at the Functional Category it can be noted that the highest rated sub-categories were Timing (using device to time exercise) and Recording steps (using device to track step count) with 21% experiences rated as positive. This was followed by: Taking blood sample (device used to take blood sample) with 8% positive; Reading heart rate, Treadmill function (using device with treadmill) and Telling time (using device to read time, i.e watch function) with approximately 3% positive experiences. It should be noted that although Recording steps and Timing were rated positive the other three main activities including Taking blood sample, Reading heart rate and Treadmill function were characterised overall more negative than positive with 13% negative, 10% negative and 3% negative respectively.

Figure 4. Medical / Health Functional and Mediation sub-categories and corresponding positive and negative percentages

Focusing on the Mediation Category it is clear that these Tasks were characterised significantly as positive overall (the positive bar graphs on the right visibly outweigh the negative bar graphs on the left overall). The highest rated sub-category was Monitoring fitness (device permitted user to monitor fitness) with 38% of experiences rated as positive. This was followed by: Motivator (device motivating user) with 23%; Monitoring health (device permitted user to monitor health) with 19% positive; Product diffuses into background (the product is used but is

not consciously thought about) with 6%; and Consciously aware of product (user is aware of presence of product) with 2%. It is important to note that the sub-categories Consciously aware of product, Another item to carry and Reliance on product (relying on the product too much) were the only activities that were reported as equal or more negative than positive, although only very slight and these categories only represented a small proportion of activities experienced.

DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The study and its findings provide significant contributions to the evolving emotional experience of interaction with PIDs. One fundamental aspect of this research is that it explored emotional experiences in context over an extended period of time (six months). This differs from many other studies in the area, which focus on investigating emotional responses to products at a single point in time (Desmet, 2002; Stelmaszewska, Blanford & Fields, 2005; Hassenzahl, Diefenbach & Goritz, 2010) or a far smaller period of time. Among the few exceptions to this are the studies conducted by Karapanos et al. (2009) that explored peoples use of mobile telephones over a 4 week exploratory study and another (Karapanos et al, 2010) that studied users with mobile telephones over the course of six months. The current study contributes to this area of research by exploring different portable devices than reported in literature. The importance of exploring emotional experiences longitudinally is that it attempts to capture a more realistic version of emotional experiences in context as well as capture the complexity and richness of these experiences.

The study also contributes by outlining specific tasks that lead to positive emotional experiences with the two product types. Generally speaking it can be noted that Mediation type activities are characterised overwhelmingly more positive than Functional activities as there were less negative experiences recorded.

IMPLICATIONS FOR FUNCTIONAL ACTIVITIES

Within the Functional Tasks for media PIDs the major positive experience were Music / Songs (listening to music), Contacting people (making calls and sending texts) and Generic work function (using device for

work-related purposes). For medical PIDs it was Timing (using device to time exercise), Recording steps (using device to track step count), and Taking blood sample. These Tasks represent some of the core functions of what the devices should do. For instance for MP3 players the key function it should allow is listening to music, while for PDAs (with mobile telephone capabilities) the core function is work and communication. With the medical device the pedometer's core function is to record steps while the blood-glucose monitor is designed to read blood samples for users. The only device that does not fit this premise is the heart-rate monitor in which its assumed core function, reading heart rate, was characterised as more negative than positive. An explanation for this might be due to the fact that although the device is called a "heart-rate monitor" it is used mainly by people exercising to read their heart rate and timing exercises. It is proposed that it might be this reason that Timing was characterised as positive in nature.

The implications are relevant when it comes to future interactive device design. Research conducted by Rust, Thompson & Hamilton (2006) reports on what is termed "feature fatigue" or "feature creep" in which an increase in the number of features and functions had a negative effect on perceived usability (Thompson, Hamilton & Rust, 2005).

This study takes this one step further and suggests that adding superfluous features and functions to products may in fact lead to negative emotional experiences over time, while doing what the product is designed to do best (its core function) may lead to positive emotional experiences over time. For media PIDs findings showed that listening to music should be the core function of the MP3 player while contacting people and allowing users the ability to perform work with the device are important aspects that potentially lead to positive experiences. For medical PIDs core functions including the ability for users to time their exercises using heart-rate monitors, for pedometers to record steps effectively and for blood-glucose monitors to take blood samples easily are critical functions of the device that lead to positive experiences. It is suggested that if the aim is to facilitate positive emotional experiences the device

should do its primary function very well without too much complexity or extraneous functions and features.

IMPLICATIONS FOR MEDIATION ACTIVITIES

Exploring the Mediation activities the major positive experiences include Escape (device facilitating escapism) and Relaxation (device allowed user to relax) for media PIDs while for medical devices Monitoring fitness (device permitted user to monitor fitness), Motivator (device motivating user) and Monitoring health (device permitted user to monitor health) were the most positively characterised.

The experience design approach has, for some time, commented on the importance of mediation type experiences of the user-product relationship. Yoo (2010) discusses this within what is termed 'experiential computing'. As Yoo highlights: "...in experiential computing, artifacts with embedded computing capabilities directly mediate the user's experience... User needs are, therefore, much broader than informational needs... reflecting deeper basic human needs and values (p.217)."

This suggests that devices, whether designed for this express purpose or not, mediate deeper user needs and values. Likewise the idea of products as mediator links directly with Activity Theory outlined earlier (Nardi, 1996).

As designers these deeper aspects should be considered from the outset. If the product facilitates genuine user desires and goals then it will lead to positive experiences. But what are these "genuine" user experiences? The implications for design from these findings are valuable. The results here point to specific activities for two product categories. For media / entertainment PIDs findings indicate that activities facilitating escape and relaxation are perceived as positive over time. For medical / health PIDs devices that assist users in monitoring their fitness and health, and motivate them to exercise will lead to positive experiences.

CONCLUSION

This paper presented a longitudinal study conducted that explored the emotional experience of two product

categories including media / entertainment PIDs (MP3 players and PDAs with mobile telephone functionality) and medical / health PIDs (blood-glucose monitors, pedometers and heart-rate monitors). For both PID types Feature related activities were mentioned most frequently and were identified as negative in nature. For media PIDs the second most mentioned category was Functional and identified as mostly positive. Mediation type activities were identified as overwhelmingly positive for both media and medical PIDs while Auxiliary activities, although making up a small part of the experiences, were characterised as significantly negative in nature.

This paper presented further findings and outlines positive emotional experiences of specific activities within the Functional and Mediation categories. Findings showed that sub-categories including Music / Songs (listening to music), Contacting people (making calls and sending texts) and Generic work function (using device for work-related purposes) were characterised as positive within the Functional category for media/entertainment PIDs. Sub-categories including Timing (using device to time exercise), Recording steps (using device to track step count), and Taking blood sample were perceived as the most positive in nature for the medical/health PIDs. Within the Mediation category Escape (device facilitating escapism) and Relaxation (device allowed user to relax) were significantly positive for media PIDs while for medical PIDs Monitoring fitness (device permitted user to monitor fitness), Motivator (device motivating user) and Monitoring health (device permitted user to monitor health) were the most positively characterised Tasks.

It is envisioned that the findings regarding positive emotional experiences presented here contribute and build on existing knowledge of emotional experience with products, especially with PIDs. The findings identified contribute to the design fields. The findings presented are relevant for media PIDs as it supports and builds on previous studies (Rust, et. al. 2006) suggesting that products should be designed primarily for their core purpose and that introducing other peripheral functions and features may confuse and ultimately detract from the overall emotional experience. Further, for medical PIDs it seems to be

more critical to design for positive emotional experiences as this has implications for general health and well-being of the user. Emotions affect the way people feel about their health at a psychological, physical and physiological level (Mayne, 2001). Researchers have also argued that well designed medical products lead to increased patient adherence to medical regimes and that design takes on a crucial role in patient therapy (Gloyd, 2003).

It is hoped the findings discussed here, alongside findings outlined in previous papers (Gomez et al., 2009, 2010, 2011), provides designers with a better understanding of what helps to facilitate and mediate positive experiences between users and PIDs so as to better design for enjoyable and pleasurable experiences in everyday contexts.

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